

MARIA

74, living with her daughter, Sofia, and her family

SOFIA

38, informal caregiver

Motivation

Maria is motivated through Sofia, who sees mHealth app as a way to stay organised and reduce the stress of caregiving.

Goal

She wants Sofia to easily track her health and receive reminders that support her care without adding extra burden.

Pain-points

Maria cannot use the app herself and depends fully on Sofia, who may feel overwhelmed by confusing or time-consuming app features.

Health situation

Maria is in the middle stages of Alzheimer's, facing progressive memory loss that sometimes leaves her unable to recognize close relatives and friends.

Health attitude

Due to her condition, Maria lacks awareness of her health status and cannot make decisions about her care. Sofia steps in as her primary caregiver and responsible taking care of her health-related tasks.

Cultural differences

Maria has a deep connection to her heritage and finds comfort in maintaining her cultural traditions. She celebrates traditional holidays with her family and close friends.

Level of dependency

Given Maria's total dependence on Sofia, she has entrusted her daughter with full access to her health information. Sofia makes most decisions on her behalf, seeking solutions that enhance Maria's quality of life while balancing the complexities of caregiving.

Trust in mHealth apps

Maria does not interact with technology, relying entirely on Sofia to manage mHealth app on her behalf. Sofia is willing to try the app as a way to support her mother's care, provided they are user-friendly and reliable.

Involvement in mHealth apps

Maria's declining cognitive skills make it impossible for her to independently use mHealth apps. As a result, she depends entirely on Sofia to interact with the app on her behalf

DANIEL

65, lives alone with his cat, Cookie

A veteran

Two children living in the same city

Motivation

Daniel is motivated by his wish to stay independent, reassured by friends' experiences with mHealth apps and his children's encouragement.

Goal

He wants the app to provide simple, trustworthy insights into his blood pressure and kidney health, without feeling judged or overloaded.

Pain-points

Skepticism and frustration with complex features make him hesitant to use the app, and excessive reminders can feel intrusive.

Health situation

Daniel is managing high blood pressure, but his reluctance to follow medical advice has led to complications, including the onset of kidney issues. He is generally capable of handling daily tasks, but when his condition worsens, he occasionally needs help.

Health attitude

Although Daniel is aware of his health challenges, he struggles to follow through with his doctor's recommendations. This reluctance has contributed to the progression of his hypertension.

Cultural differences

His children visit him on weekends, and he regularly spends time at the nearby RSL club with fellow veterans. These visits provide a chance to share stories and discuss health-related topics, including their experiences with mHealth apps.

Level of dependency

Daniel is mostly independent but relies on a home care assistant for weekly meal preparation and his children for help understanding health information and making informed decisions. This support requires him to share most of his health information to ensure effective care and decision-making.

Trust in mHealth apps

Daniel is skeptical about mHealth apps, believing they cannot replace face-to-face interactions with his doctor. However, after hearing positive feedback from friends at the RSL club, he installed an app on his smartphone.

Involvement in mHealth apps

As a newcomer to mHealth apps, Daniel has limited interest in exploring its features. His skepticism and lack of familiarity reduce his motivation to engage with the app actively.

EMMA

41, lives near city center with her husband, Ari, and their dog, Blossom

A freelance graphic designer

Motivation

Emma is motivated by the need to manage her diabetes efficiently and seamlessly alongside her busy work and personal life.

Goal

She wants reliable alerts, clear data visualisations, and easy integration with her devices to maintain control and independence.

Pain-points

Emma dislikes poorly designed apps, excessive notifications, and worries about the privacy of her sensitive health data.

Health situation

Diagnosed with Type 1 diabetes at the age of six, Emma has been using an insulin pump since she was seven. Managing her condition has been a long-term part of her life, and she has developed a strong understanding of how to maintain her health.

Health attitude

She strictly follows a diabetes-friendly diet and incorporates regular exercise into her routine, including runs or gym sessions with her dog, Blossom.

Cultural differences

Emma values her independence and enjoys spending time alone or with her dog. While she occasionally has dinner with her close friends, she prefers solitary activities like walking in the park or experimenting with new healthy recipes in her spare time.

Level of dependency

Emma lives independently without the need for a caregiver, maintaining regular communication with her mother. She values her privacy, sharing health-related information only with her husband and doctor.

Trust in mHealth apps

With her familiarity with digital health technology, Emma trusts mHealth apps and believes they offer significant benefits. She views them as valuable tools to help manage her diabetes and maintain her overall health.

Involvement in mHealth apps

As a graphic designer, Emma's strong technology literacy allows her to navigate mHealth apps effortlessly.

Dimension	Keywords	Reference
Health situation	"symptom", "sugar spike", "monitor level", "fatigue", "tiredness", "diabetes log", "medicine", "vision problem", "carbs", "anxious", "anxiety", "diabetic diet", "meal plan", "nutrition", "portion", "insulin injection", "medication", "HbA1c", "A1c", "weight change", "glycemic index", "hospital", "lifestyle"	Andrew J. Karter, Shantanu Nundy, Melissa M. Parker, Howard H. Moffet, Elbert S. Huang: Incidence of Remission in Adults With Type 2 Diabetes: The Diabetes & Aging Study. Diabetes Care 1 December 2014; 37 (12): 3188–3195. https://doi.org/10.2337/dc14-0874
Health attitude	"aware", "awareness", "behaviour", "engage", "improve", "monitoring", "tracking", "commitment", "literacy", "wellness", "motivation", "conscious", "prevent"	Jayanti, R.K., Burns, A.C. The antecedents of preventive health care behavior: An empirical study. J. of the Acad. Mark. Sci. 26, 6–15 (1998). https://doi.org/10.1177/0092070398261002
Cultural Differences	"share", "authority", "autonomy", "community", "personal", "language", "culture", "freedom", "independent", "independence"	W.A Arrindell. Culture's consequences: Comparing values, behaviors, institutions, and organizations across nations: Geert Hofstede. Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks, California, 2001. ISSN 0005-7967. https://doi.org/10.1016/S0005-7967(02)00184-5.
Level of Dependency	"carer", "caregiver", "husband", "wife", "family", "son", "daughter", "decision", "privacy", "protect", "independence", "custom", "privacy", "control", "reliance", "family support", "security", "sensitive information", "confidentiality", "assistance", "self-monitoring", "kid", "children", "child", "parent"	Garcia Reyes E, Kelly R, Buchanan G, Waycott J. Understanding Older Adults' Experiences With Technologies for Health Self-management: Interview Study JMIR Aging 2023;6:e43197. URL: https://aging.jmir.org/2023/1/e43197. DOI: 10.2196/43197 Sebastiaan T.M. Peek, Eveline J.M. Wouters, Joost van Hoof, Katrien G. Luijkx, Hennie R. Boeije, Hubertus J.M. Vrijhoef. Factors influencing acceptance of technology for aging in place: A systematic review. International Journal of Medical Informatics. Volume 83, Issue 4, 2014, Pages 235-248. ISSN 1386-5056. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2014.01.004.
Trust in mHealth Apps	"trust", "trustworthy", "privacy", "secure", "security", "concern", "credible", "credibility", "cautious", "optimist", "optimism", "fear", "reliable", "comprehensive", "protect", "protection", "valid", "transparency", "fulfil", "fail", "support", "responsive"	Komiak, S. Y. X., & Benbasat, I. (2006). The Effects of Personalization and Familiarity on Trust and Adoption of Recommendation Agents. MIS Quarterly, 30(4), 941–960. https://doi.org/10.2307/25148760 Müller, R., Primc, N. & Kuhn, E. 'You have to put a lot of trust in me': autonomy, trust, and trustworthiness in the context of mobile apps for mental health. Med Health Care and Philos 26, 313–324 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1007/s11019-023-10146-y
User Involvement with the App	"interaction", "setting", "usage", "involve", "flexible", "setup", "automatic", "customisation", "customise", "feature", "adjustment", "error", "experience", "friendly", "intuitive", "engaged"	Sari Kujala and Talya Miron-Shatz. 2015. The evolving role of expectations in long-term user experience. In Proceedings of the 19th International Academic Mindtrek Conference (AcademicMindTrek '15). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 167–174. https://doi.org/10.1145/2818187.2818271